

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF THE HOTEL AND CATERING SERVICES SECTOR IN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Annotatation. The article describes important aspects related to modern methodological approaches of econometric research of development of tourism, hotel and catering services. In particular, a grouped system of indicators for a comprehensive economic analysis of the activities of tourism and catering enterprises, a scenario for the classification of the analysis of enterprises' activities by criteria, and a scheme for forming a set of synergistic factors of development are proposed. Today, tourism and hotel services are an important component of the global economy and play a significant role in the economic development of countries and regions. The development of this sector serves not only economic growth, but also the development of social and cultural aspects. However, the catering industry of tourism and hotel services also deserves great attention from an environmental point of view. In recent years, issues of environmental sustainability have become one of the most important problems in the world. Due to factors such as global warming, climate changes, and limited natural resources, there is a need to reduce the ecological footprint of tourism and catering services. Therefore, it is important to assess the environmental characteristics of this area and develop environmentally friendly approaches.

Key words: econometric model, tourism, hotel and catering, complex economic analysis, system of indicators, synergistic factors, criteria of analysis classification.

Introduction. In recent years, our country has been paying increasing attention to the development of services, in particular, tourism, hotel and catering services. This is due to the great importance of this sector in improving the quality of life of the population, increasing the tourism potential of our country, forming modern rural and urban infrastructure, increasing the employment rate, and in general, increasing the effectiveness of reforms aimed at ensuring economic stability. The Development

Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 also places special emphasis on the development of the service sector, including the development of points of provision of services such as household and catering services, which are in high daily demand by the population, and roadside services in urban and district centers, as part of Goal 34[2]. It also envisages the implementation of special programs to improve the lifestyle of the population, increasing the tourism potential of the regions of the Republic, depending on the improvement of mechanisms for the development of hotels and similar accommodation and catering services, comprehensive support for the activities of service entities in the sector, and providing them with additional benefits.

In today's innovative development environment based on the principle of digitalization of economic sectors, econometric research is given priority in identifying priority areas of development based on the introduction of new methods and innovative technologies into the hotel and catering industry, and optimal use of existing regional economic potential.

Literature Review. In the studies of foreign scientists, there are groupings of trends in the development of the hotel market. These trends are divided into groups of varying numbers. Against the background of tourism development, four main models of organizing hotel and catering activities are distinguished for each geographical latitude. B. Brocherton, J. Woolfenden, B. Himmet conducted extensive research on the development trends of hotels and catering, indicators of personnel development. In them, the development of potential personnel is considered the main indicator in the development of the industry[3].

The scientific views of economist Professor Mukhitdinov Kh. S., Rakhimov A. N., Rakhimov A., Juraev F. D., Makhmatkulov put forward the idea that any socio-economic, financial, technical-technological, information, intellectual, software resources can be transformed into innovative resources under the influence of the laws of renewal[4].

The issues of modeling and forecasting the development of hotel and catering services, multi-criteria optimization of production, regional development of hotels and catering and classification of its multi-factor empirical models have occupied a wide place in the scientific research of Rakhimov, A.N., Juraev, F.D., Rakhimov A.M., Makhmanazarovna, R.M., S.N. Sultanov, G.Kh. Makhmatkulov[8].

Research Methodology. The research process used statistical data study and economic comparison and analysis, logical thinking, scientific abstraction, selective

observation, analysis and synthesis, the least squares method, correlation and regression analysis methods.

Analysis and discussion of results. Our article used analysis methods based on various criteria, including financial-economic, economic-statistical, prospective and retrospective, factor, economic-mathematical, stochastic, general and selective analyses by industry sector. The development of accommodation and catering services has different development factors depending on the characteristics of space and time. This is related to the directions of development. Analysis of the financial and economic activities of service enterprises is carried out based on certain criteria, based on the content and essence of the goals and objectives of the activity. In particular, analysis by industry, taking into account the specific characteristics of hotel and catering services, prospective analysis, aimed at substantiating management decisions and activity planning functions up to the implementation of economic activities, used to calculate prospective indicators, retrospective analysis, used to monitor the state of implementation of planned tasks during the ongoing activities, identify unused, available reserve resources, and assess the results of current activities, analysis at the level of one farm and inter-farm, socio-economic analysis, used to study the interrelationship of financial, economic and technical processes focused on financial aspects and results, as well as socio-economic analysis, which shows the dependence of technical, socio-economic processes, their impact on the activities of the enterprise, as well as economic-ecological, economic-statistical analysis, which is distinguished by the method of study, factorial, diagnostic, causal, Economic-mathematical, stochastic analyses, continuous and selective analyses differentiated according to the scope of the objects under study create a scenario for economic analysis according to the criteria.

In our opinion, any economic sector relies on four types of development: potential, which is associated with the country's uniqueness and internal capabilities; technological, based on scientific achievements, tools applied to the industry, and technical and technological experience; innovative, which is associated with the broad thinking of humanity, the ability to create innovations, and the effective use of modern technologies; and their generalized synergistic development directions based on certain algorithms and principles.

Determining these development directions requires a comprehensive formulation of a number of socio-economic issues, and the selection of the optimal solution is based on in-depth scientific analysis, various research methods and scientific results. The fact that the object does not consist of a single integral aspect

determines its complexity. The presence of economic, social, and political aspects of the development of housing and public catering services for the population creates a complex system of the object. At the same time, this system cannot be considered complete, that is, structurally, parametrically determined. In this case, the importance of modeling theory in studying the development of the sector, if it is taken into account that it is an economic object, then the importance of the theory, methods, and approaches of econometric modeling increases.

The production of finished factors is limited to focusing on the use characterized by a certain development direction. The reason for this is the convenience of providing solid directions specific to the type of development with scientific foundations based on decisions related to this set. However, the development of the industry has a synergistic nature, and here we consider that in order to achieve the research process, without denying all the episodes achieved in the current year, we only need to identify the direction of improvement. In this sense, the optimal solution for the selection of factors in the process is to form a synergy of the influence of factors that have priority status in various areas of development. In the process, it is possible to form a set of synergistic factors. Also, all variables of the development of the sector in real time or in social reality, which are uncertain, sufficiently complex, prone to nonlinearity, and unbalanced, are included. In our opinion, the set of internal and external factors related to the whole system, the level and quantitative scale of which change while maintaining the nature of the impact in a dynamic process, is considered a set of synergistic factors in econometric research. As a result of our studies related to the theoretical substantiation of the development of hotel and catering services, we proposed the following scheme for the formation of a set of synergistic factors in our research.

In the systematic study of the set of synergistic factors considered as the identification of priority factors, the most effective are sectoral analysis by sectoral sign, as well as prospective and retrospective analyses differentiated by time sign. As noted above, sectoral analysis is carried out taking into account the specific characteristics of a particular sector of the economy.

Conclusion and recommendations. In general, econometric research widely uses econometric methods for quantitative systematic study of an area (object), that is, for constructing group relationships between system elements, assessing their impact on the main or partial effectiveness, highlighting the importance of derivative indicators, and identifying sources of influence, and economic and statistical analysis methods for studying development trends.

In recent years, the study of socio-economic processes using models has become increasingly important. It is appropriate to divide the most commonly used models in the development of economic sectors into three types, depending on the purpose of construction, scope of application and effectiveness.

To these:

1) classical models that structurally express the interconnected, branched properties of social elements, which are applied in wide areas of development, have the property of unifying in the development of models for determining the response to new directions of development of the sector;

2) development models that are oriented towards a specific object, expressing a new view of the integrated system, or its independent system, in a structural-parametric way;

3) quantitatively expressed models that are part of or participate in the mechanism for implementing the main goal of development, determine the response of the system to input variables, and provide a scientific justification of reality.

Hotel and catering services have a significant economic impact on the development of tourism. Through the integration of these sectors and the provision of quality services, it is possible to develop not only the tourism sector, but also the local economy. Investments, job creation and cooperation with local producers are important aspects of these sectors.

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